

Public attitudes on vaccines and seasonal influenza vaccination in Bulgaria

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Abstract

Vaccination has been scientifically proven to be the safest and most effective means of protection against influenza and of limiting the spread of the virus that causes it. Based on an anonymous questionnaire-based survey conducted among 1038 Bulgarian citizens, we found that only 16.76% had been vaccinated against seasonal influenza, while only 26.69% expressed willingness to be vaccinated in the future. A total of 79.48% believed that the influenza vaccine should only be recommended, with 70.0% of women and 79.73% of men supporting this approach to immunisation coverage. Overall, 64.84% expressed interest in the effects of vaccines. Women showed less interest in vaccine effectiveness than men – with 63.99% of women, compared to 68.06% of men, giving a positive response. The general practitioner was identified as the main source of information on issues related to the effectiveness of seasonal influenza vaccines by more than half of the respondents (51.93%), while 27.17% relied on information found on the Internet.

Keywords

influenza, unformedness, vaccines

Introduction

Seasonal influenza can cause significant complications and has a serious impact on public health, notably by increasing morbidity, hospitalisations, and mortality, as well as exacerbating chronic conditions. According to global statistics, around 70 000 deaths caused by influenza are recorded annually in European Union (EU) Member States, with up to 90% of these occurring in people over 65, mostly those with comorbidities. Annually, seasonal

influenza epidemics are responsible for 3 to 5 million severe cases worldwide. Seasonal influenza is among the leading causes of mortality, with an estimated 290 000 to 650 000 deaths worldwide every year. In 2025, the season is particularly severe, resulting in numerous hospitalisations (Al-Hajjar 2025).

The main means of preventing influenza and reducing morbidity, mortality, and severe complications is vaccination prophylaxis. Influenza vaccination has scientifically proven benefits for individual and public health,

significantly reducing morbidity, the risk of severe complications, hospitalisations, and mortality, particularly among high-risk groups. The influenza vaccine has been shown to reduce the risk of infection and severe courses of the disease, including a reduction in hospitalisations of 55–78% among children and adults, according to data from the 2024–2025 season (Frutos et al. 2025).

The goal of this article is to present and analyse public attitudes to vaccines and influenza vaccination in our country.

In order to achieve the goal of the study, the following tasks were set:

1. Presenting the role that influenza immunisation plays in public health.
2. Surveying respondents' willingness to be vaccinated.
3. Researching respondents' opinion on whether influenza vaccination should be mandatory or recommended.
4. Researching respondents' knowledge of the effects of influenza vaccines.

Methods

An anonymous questionnaire-based survey was conducted via Google Forms between 01 January 2025 and 01 April 2025. The anonymity of participants was fully maintained, in accordance with all requirements and the ethical code of confidentiality. A total of 1038 randomly selected individuals aged between 18 and 69+ participated in the study.

Descriptive and analytical statistical methods were used. The shape of the distribution was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. To identify relationships between categorical variables, Pearson's chi-square test and Fisher's exact test were applied. A P value of <0.05 was assumed to indicate statistical significance. The SPSS 20 software package was used for the relevant analyses and data processing.

Results and discussion

Influenza is the most commonly reported infectious disease for which there is a vaccine. The disease affects certain vulnerable groups of the population – the elderly, young children, patients with comorbidities, and pregnant women. The number of influenza cases exceeds the number of all other infections combined by several times.

Influenza is an acute viral infection characterised by severe intoxication – high fever, headache, severe muscle pain, and catarrhal inflammation of the upper respiratory tract. Uncomplicated cases result in a temporary inability to work for several days to a week, without specific treatment. Complications can be fatal, especially in so-called risk groups – young children, adults over 65, immunosuppressed individuals, and people suffering from diabetes, hypertension, hypercholesterolaemia, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). For these groups, the risk of a severe and prolonged course, complications, and even death is highest.

The influenza A virus has caused a number of severe pandemics in the last century. The Spanish flu was a pandemic in 1918 that killed between 50 and 100 million people, while the Asian flu and the Hong Kong flu in 1957 and 1968 caused a total of 4 to 8 million deaths. During the 2009 influenza pandemic caused by the A/H1N1 strain, an estimated 150 000 people died, and, unlike typical influenza seasons, 80% of those who died were under 65 (Dawood et al. 2012).

Immunisation coverage for this infectious disease varies considerably across European countries. With the introduction of the National Program for Improving Seasonal Influenza Vaccination, immunisation coverage for seasonal influenza among persons aged 65 and over, who are the target group of the programme, was achieved as follows: 2019 – 7.8%, 2020 – 11.4%, and 2021 – 13.24% (<https://plusmen.bg/bg/national-programs/flu>). The reasons for the low immunisation coverage in our country may be diverse – anti-vaccination sentiments, insufficient informedness on vaccine effectiveness, fear of side effects, or underestimation of the severity of the disease and its consequences. The programme's goal is to achieve 35% influenza vaccination coverage among the target group by 2026.

Influenza vaccination is recognised as the most effective tool for preventing the spread of seasonal influenza. Currently, the European Council recommends that 75% vaccination coverage for seasonal influenza be achieved in elderly patients (>65 years) and, ideally, in all patients over 6 months of age who have chronic diseases (Blank et al. 2012; Council of the European Communities 2014, 2015). It is assumed that a vaccination coverage of 75% in populations at risk of influenza-related complications can be used as a first step towards increasing coverage for all patients (Kassianos 2015; Meier et al. 2000).

Some countries, such as the United Kingdom (Preaud et al. 2014; Public Health England 2014a, 2014b) and the Netherlands (Dutch College of General Practitioners 2015), prepare and regularly update their guidelines for influenza vaccination. There is considerable variation in the provision of seasonal influenza vaccines across Europe and in rates of influenza vaccination coverage (ECDC 2025). In a special report, the European Commission emphasised the need for action at both EU and Member State levels to reap the full benefits of seasonal influenza vaccination, recommending that Member States share their experience (Council of the European Communities 2014).

Essential information concerning influenza vaccination – including recommendations, special cases, contraindications, effectiveness, safety, timing, and types of vaccines – should be better presented. The work of specialists involved in influenza vaccination would be greatly improved if information on influenza immunisation – including details on patients in at-risk groups, notification processes, product logistics, maintenance of registers, and answers to frequently asked questions – were made more widely available.

The questionnaire survey covered 1038 respondents, of whom 822 were women (79.19%) and 216 were men (20.81%). The distribution of respondents according to place of residence shows that the largest proportion were

from Sofia (66.38%), followed by those living in provincial centre cities (23.60%) and smaller towns (5.97%) (Fig. 1). The average age of the respondents was 45.1609 (± 0.9283).

Figure 1. Respondent distribution according to place of birth.

The distribution of respondents according to their social status shows that the largest number and proportion are employed – 729 respondents (70.23%), while inactive persons (not working and not seeking employment) account for only 0.48%. Unemployed individuals seeking work account for 1.83%, while students account for 13.68%. The relative share of pensioners in our study is 12.81% (Table 1).

Table 1. The social status of the respondents.

Social status	Number	Relative share in %
Student	142	13.68%
Inactive (doesn't work and is not actively seeking employment)	5	0.48%
Unemployed (actively seeking employment)	19	1.83%
Working (self-employed or employed)	729	70.23%
Retired	133	12.81%
Retired due to illness	10	0.96%
Total	1038	100%

In terms of educational attainment, the largest number and proportion of respondents are those with higher education (bachelor's and master's degrees) – 551 respondents (50.8%), while the smallest proportion is observed among respondents with primary education – one respondent (0.10%) – and those with basic education – 11 respondents (1.06%). Almost one third of the respondents (29.77%, or 309) have secondary education, 87 respondents (8.38%) have a vocational bachelor's degree, and 79 respondents (7.61%) have a doctoral degree. Studying the educational level of respondents is important for understanding the questions and answering them correctly, as well as for identifying connections and dependencies between individual questions.

The number of married individuals who participated in the survey was 597 (57.51%), while the number of unmarried respondents was 283 (27.26%), followed by divorced respondents (91; 8.77%) and widowed respondents (67; 6.45%).

Although a large proportion of the population expresses fears related to influenza, only a small percentage of respondents reported being vaccinated – 16.76% (174). Pearson's chi-square test revealed a statistically significant correlation between gender and vaccination status, with a test value of $\chi^2 = 56.841$ and a significance level of $p < 0.001$. Fig. 2 shows that, within the unvaccinated group, the proportion of women (83.56%) exceeds that of men (16.44%) by approximately sixfold.

Fisher's exact test showed a statistically significant correlation between social status and seasonal influenza vaccination, with a test value of 148.236 and a significance level of $p < 0.001$. Fig. 3 shows that, among the actively employed population, the proportion of unvaccinated individuals (75.46% of the unvaccinated) exceeds the proportion of vaccinated individuals (44.25% of the vaccinated). Conversely, among retired respondents, this ratio is reversed, with the proportion of vaccinated individuals (44.83%) exceeding that of unvaccinated individuals (6.37%) by approximately sevenfold (Fig. 3). This correlation and difference can be explained by the adopted National Program for Improving Vaccine Prophylaxis in People Aged 65 and Over.

Figure 2. Respondent distribution according to vaccination status and sex.

Figure 3. Relationship between vaccination status and social status of respondents.

Student’s parametric t-test was used to explore the relationship between age in the vaccinated and unvaccinated groups by comparing a quantitative variable between two unrelated groups. Table 2 presents the results of this analysis.

Table 2. Comparison of the average age of respondents according to vaccination status.

Have you been vaccinated against seasonal influenza?	Number	Average age	p
Unvaccinated	864	42.5093 (± 0.8921)	<0.001
Vaccinate	174	58.3276 (± 2.5607)	

The test shows a statistically significant difference in the mean age values (MEAN_unvaccinated = 42.6 (± 0.8921))

years; MEAN_vaccinated = 58.3 (± 2.5607) years), with a test result of $t = -11.507$ and $p < 0.001$. The average age of vaccinated respondents is 16 years higher than that of unvaccinated respondents (Fig. 4). The higher age of vaccinated respondents can be explained by the fact that a higher proportion of vaccinated individuals is found in the retiree group, while unvaccinated individuals predominate in the employed group (Fig. 3).

When asked, “Would you get vaccinated against seasonal influenza in the future?”, only 26.69% of respondents gave a positive answer. More than half of the respondents (56.55%) answered this question with “no”, while 16.76% did not provide an answer.

The reasons why Bulgarians do not get vaccinated against seasonal influenza are multifaceted, with the main factors

Figure 4. Box plot diagram of age in vaccinated and unvaccinated groups.

being lack of trust in the vaccine, low levels of awareness, financial barriers, limited support from healthcare professionals, possible side effects following vaccination, and opposition to vaccination. These and other factors influence the decision of more than half of the adult population (56.55%) not to get vaccinated, according to our research.

In a study conducted in Varna among 120 respondents in 2018 by Ermenlieva et al., it was found that 70% of respondents had never been vaccinated against seasonal influenza in their lifetime, with 53.7% of unvaccinated individuals citing lack of trust in the vaccine as the main reason (Ermenlieva et al. 2019).

Another study conducted between November 2016 and February 2017 by Rangelova et al., covering 545 respondents over the age of 18 in the city of Burgas, reported the following reasons for non-vaccination: “the vaccine is not effective” (30.5%), “influenza is not that dangerous” (28.2%), “lack of sufficient information” (27.6%), and “opposition to vaccines” (15.2%) (Rangelova et al. 2018).

A more extensive information campaign on vaccines is needed, focusing on education regarding their characteristics and the types appropriate for different population groups. It is important that such a campaign be conducted by experts in the field who can explain vaccine-related issues of interest to the population in accessible language. As a result, attitudes towards vaccination among some individuals are likely to change, and the proportion of vaccinated individuals may increase.

We were also interested in respondents' opinions on whether vaccination against seasonal influenza should be mandatory or recommended. A question addressing this issue was included in the questionnaire. The results are shown in Fig. 5.

The absolute number and relative proportion of respondents who believe that the vaccine should only be

recommended are significantly higher, accounting for 75.14% in total. Of these, 70.0% are women and 79.73% are men.

A total of 19.54% of respondents stated that the seasonal influenza vaccine should be mandatory. The relative proportion of women giving this response is 23.0%, while that of men is 14.86%.

We explored whether respondents' opinions on the question, “Should vaccines be mandatory or recommended?” were related to vaccination status.

The chi-square test shows a statistically significant relationship between the two variables, with a test result of $\chi^2 = 63.339$ and $p < 0.001$.

The results demonstrate that among respondents who believe vaccination should be mandatory, the ratio of vaccinated to unvaccinated individuals is 1:1. In contrast, among those who believe vaccination should be recommended, the ratio is approximately 1:6, with unvaccinated individuals forming the larger proportion (Fig. 6). It can be assumed that, despite believing vaccination should only be recommended, many respondents do not get vaccinated for various reasons.

When asked, “Are you interested in how seasonal influenza vaccines work?”, 64.84% of respondents gave an affirmative answer. Women showed less interest in vaccine effectiveness than men, with 63.99% of women and 68.06% of men providing a positive response.

The pattern is reversed among those who gave a negative answer, which accounted for 35.16% of respondents. Among these, 36.02% were women and 31.94% were men.

The results of the study indicate a high level of interest in issues related to the effectiveness of seasonal influenza vaccines. The general practitioner is the main source of information on these issues for 51.93% of respondents, while 27.17% rely on information found on the Internet. The number of respondents using the Internet as a source of information

Figure 5. Respondent distribution according to opinions on whether vaccination should be mandatory.

Figure 6. Relationship between vaccination status and respondents' opinions on whether the seasonal influenza vaccine should be mandatory or recommended.

increases with decreasing age and is higher among individuals living in larger cities. A total of 20.62% obtain information from the National Health Information System, while television ranks as the fourth most common source, at 13.10%. Only five respondents (0.48%) reported not being interested in the topic or seeking information (Fig. 7).

Patients regard general practitioners as the most important and trusted source of information on influenza vaccination, as established in numerous scientific studies and international analyses. The trust that patients place in their physicians increases the likelihood that they will follow immunisation recommendations and enhances vaccination coverage in at-risk groups. General practitioners can provide personalised information tailored to patients' health status, age, chronic conditions, and specific medical needs, thereby recommending the most appropriate vaccine type and providing guidance on contraindications (Grohskopf et al. 2024; Kalarikkal and Jaishankar 2025).

Patients are more likely to trust specific medical advice given by a physician who regularly monitors their health, and this form of direct communication is considered a reliable source of information according to national and European studies (Ermenlieva et al. 2019).

If patients receive an active recommendation from their general practitioner, the probability of immunisation increases by up to 70% among elderly and chronically ill individuals.

General practitioners not only provide information on vaccine effectiveness, safety, and available types but also manage the organisation, timing, and access to vaccination and, when necessary, offer consultations on specific cases or possible side effects. General practitioners therefore play a key role in informing and motivating people to receive influenza vaccination, and effective doctor-patient communication is a fundamental mechanism for increasing vaccination coverage.

Figure 7. Respondent distribution according to sources of information on vaccine effectiveness.

Conclusion

Achieving high vaccination coverage against seasonal influenza in the population contributes to reducing the spread of the virus and lessens the likelihood of the emergence of new viral strains.

Our country continues to rank last in the European Union in terms of the number of vaccinated citizens, despite conclusive scientific and statistical data demonstrating that vaccines protect against severe courses of the disease, subsequent complications, and death. These factors highlight the need to introduce larger-scale information campaigns among the population, aimed at addressing common concerns and providing clear, science-based information on vaccines and immunisation.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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Use of AI

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Data

Author: Stefan Velikov

Data type: xlsx

Explanation note: The results from survey.

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